

The Impact of Continuing Professional Development (CPD) on the Inclusion of Students with Special Educational Needs (SEN) in the Teaching and Learning of Mathematics in Primary Schools

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The National Council for Special Education (NCSE) was set up to improve the delivery of education services to persons with special educational needs with particular emphasis on children. A fundamental aspect in the delivery of this objective includes the provision of high-quality Continuous Professional Development (CPD) for teachers. This paper aims to provide readers with an overview of relevant research in this area and the guiding principles which will inform future CPD provisions for teachers in relation to both curriculum reform and the inclusion of students with special educational needs. In the context of Primary curriculum reform, this paper also sets out to examine the key considerations required to achieve an inclusive Mathematics classroom for all learners in all contexts.

Introduction

In Ireland, almost one in four children have Special Educational Needs (SEN) that can impact their learning (Banks and McCoy, 2011). This prevalence rate is derived using the broad definition of SEN in the Education for Persons with Special Educational Needs Act (2004) (EPSEN Act) which states

in relation to a person, a restriction in the capacity of the person to participate in and benefit from education on account of an enduring physical, sensory, mental health or learning disability, or any other condition which results in a person learning differently from a person without that condition. (p.6).

Teachers have a fundamental impact on whether students learn (Fullen, 2006) and, therefore, in driving curriculum reform, effective and meaningful CPD for teachers is essential. Research highlights that provision of decontextualized, once off in-service seminars to introduce new curricula is ineffective (Fung, 2000) and instead positive impactful CPD opportunities are needed for teachers (Crawford et al., 2007). The Draft Primary Curriculum Framework (NCCA, 2020) emphasises the importance of “ongoing access to, and opportunities for, high-quality and school-based continuing professional development.” (p. 28). It also addresses the idea of teacher and leader collaboration which is highlighted as “enabling and supporting teachers and school leaders to identify and prioritise school-based CPD needs alongside national priorities.” (NCCA, 2020, p.28).

Research findings consistently support the central role teachers play in the education of learners with SEN. There is evidence that the quality of teaching is one of the most important factors in learner outcomes (NCSE, 2013). The central role of the teacher in moving towards an inclusive education system is widely acknowledged; the World Report on Disability (WHO, 2011) stressed that appropriate training of mainstream teachers is crucial

for them to be confident and competent in teaching children with diverse needs. In order to promote inclusion in the redeveloped Mathematics curriculum, all teachers need to be equipped to meet the increasingly diverse needs of learners. Provision of CPD opportunities for teachers is integral to successful inclusion of all learners. The NCSE recognises the importance of providing quality and tailored support for teachers in the embedding of new curricula, as evidenced by the roll out of CPD and supports for the Primary Language Curriculum (PLC). The NCSE Primary Curriculum Team developed in-service courses and continue to provide in-school support. The PLC represents the first of the curricula to move from content objectives to learning outcomes. In the rollout of the Primary Mathematics Curriculum CPD will be needed to help teachers enact this change in their classrooms.

Supporting Inclusion through Teacher Continuing Professional Development

The Cosán Framework (Teaching Council, 2016) has highlighted inclusion as one of the key areas that should be addressed in schools through teacher CPD. There have been many important legislative and policy developments in the movement towards inclusion, both nationally and internationally, including the Salamanca Statement and Framework for Action on Special-Needs Education (1994), the Council of Europe Political Declaration (2003) and Action Plan (2006), the EPSEN Act (2004), and the United Nations International Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (2006) which Ireland signed in 2007 and ratified in 2018.

More recently, Guidelines for Primary and Post-Primary Schools; Supporting Students with Special Educational Needs in Mainstream Schools (Department of Education, 2017), highlights the central role the mainstream class teacher has in ensuring the progress and care of all students in the classroom, including students with special educational needs. It is essential that CPD with a focus on supporting students with special educational needs is made available for mainstream class teachers and not just for Special Education Teachers, Special School Teachers and Special Classes Teachers. Teacher CPD can have a positive impact on inclusion (Rose et al, 2010) but there is a need to look at teacher's knowledge as well as their attitudes and beliefs. Teacher expectations are essential to a child's success (Shevlin and Rose, 2003) and thus teacher attitudes and beliefs can be barriers to the inclusion of students with SEN in the classroom. Hodkinson (2009) argues that successful inclusion may be dependent first upon teachers' attitudes and beliefs and secondly their competence to deliver.

The NCSE offers online support and in-person training days as well as in-school support. However, very few mainstream teachers attend these courses. For example, only 7% of those who attended NCSE Term 1 Primary Teacher Professional Learning National seminars in 2020 were mainstream teachers. This was in a Covid-19 context however; that aside, it does highlight the idea of possible mandatory CPD in the area of SEN for all teachers. CPD for teachers is a common theme across a majority of NCSE Policy Advice papers (2011, 2012, 2013, 2015 and 2018). These papers often refer to research studies which recommend that teachers should have access to CPD relevant to their student's needs. NCSE acknowledges that teachers in different settings require CPD with different foci to best meet

the needs of their students (NCSE Policy Advice 2, 2011). Highlighted in these policy advice papers is the need for mandatory CPD for all teachers so they can gain the knowledge, skills and competencies which empower them to enable students with special educational needs to fulfil their potential in all contexts.

Supporting Inclusion in the Teaching and Learning of Mathematics in the Primary Classroom

Children who fail to acquire competence in basic mathematical facts tend to have negative attitudes towards mathematics and often avoid this in day-to-day living in later life. (Doherty et al., 2011). To promote and advance the teaching of mathematics for students with SEN, initial and sustained support for teachers needs to be provided so that all teachers feel confident and skilled to include all learners in the mathematics class. Effective and meaningful CPD enables teachers to negotiate each individual student's learning strengths and unique needs. It is important that teachers understand how the diverse needs of their students impact on teaching and learning in the classroom. An over emphasis on teaching specifically to the category of need can mean the focus becomes about the label and not the holistic strengths and needs of the child (Cologon, 2014). In the context of mathematics, it is known that low arithmetical attainment can be associated with a general learning difficulty, a readiness lag, or a specific learning difficulty (SLD) in numeracy, also known as dyscalculia (Neville, 2012). For example, 3–7% of all children, adolescents, and adults suffer from dyscalculia, which is a severe, persistent difficulty performing arithmetical calculations and can lead to marked difficulty in school, at work and in everyday life (Haberstroh and Schulte-Körne, 2019). Within the classroom, unfamiliarity with dyscalculia may lead to unrealistic expectations regarding accessing the class curriculum and number fact recall. Examples such as these further highlight that teachers require support to understand the different supports that students require in order to access the mathematics curriculum.

Approached to Mathematics Education for Students with SEN

Students with learning disabilities require a structured approach to mathematics as some students may learn inappropriate or incorrect strategies through incidental learning. Approaches may include direct explicit teaching and opportunities to practice different skills and strategies to consolidate learning; accommodations; universal design for learning; and differentiated instruction.

Explicit Teaching

Direct teaching, using explicit strategies, is a well recommended technique for teaching all students and works well for students with learning difficulties in Mathematics (Westwood, 2000). This approach is described as the systematic delivery of Mathematics lessons, within a structured class, using the following specific procedures; 'introducing objectives, reviewing previously learned concepts, modelling new skills, and providing guided and independent practice' (McKenna et al., 2015, p. 8). This supports teachers to apply procedure-based mathematics instruction to support all students in the classroom.

Accommodations

Accommodations in the Mathematics classrooms using assistive technology can range from low to high technology. For example, students who are deaf or hard of hearing may use an FM system, interpreter, real-time captioning and visual warning devices and there is a vast array of technology-based accommodation such as voice recognition software, switches and augmentative communication devices. It is important that effective and appropriate CPD is made available to ensure teachers know how to utilise the accommodations to support access to the Mathematics Curriculum by students with SEN.

Universal Design for Learning (UDL)

The UDL framework is one which provides multiple methods of presentation, multiple methods of expression and multiple options for engagement (Meyer and Rose, 1998). UDL enables the educator to remove barriers by anticipating the needs of all students.

“Accessibility and inclusion are embedded within all three UDL principles” (Dyjur, Ferreira, and Clancy, 2021, p.73). The broader goal of accessible pedagogy can benefit students with and without SEN (Moon et al., 2012). Connecting UDL to Mathematics curriculum development is an important goal in promoting the teaching of Mathematics for students with SEN. “Universal design for learning (UDL) is a valuable tool for the proactive planning of engaging, accessible lessons in today's diverse classrooms” (Sally, 2011, p10). Targeted CPD for teachers in this aspect of inclusive practice is a key element for determining success in applying the principles of UDL.

Differentiated Instruction

Differentiated Instruction and UDL are not mutually exclusive. Differentiation is a process by which all pupils are enabled to engage in the curriculum by the provision of learning tasks and activities that are tailored to their needs and abilities. Willis and Mann (2000, p. 1) state that “differentiation is a teaching philosophy based on the premise that teachers should adapt instruction to pupil differences”. Differentiation should be seen in terms of different styles and strengths of pupils and not on a hierarchy of abilities. Activities, methodology, environment, resources and outcomes can be varied to take into account the diverse range of interests, needs and experience of the pupils. Widodo, Prihatiningsih and Taufiq (2021) point to the importance of a range of resources and the use of various learning media in learning mathematics. Creating multiple pathways for learning through differentiated instruction as part of the daily learning experience is essential in advancing the teaching of mathematics for students with SEN. Blending the concepts of UDL and differentiated instruction with an inclusive curriculum for all is the ultimate goal in terms of engaging students in opportunities to access mathematics.

Conclusion

It is important that teachers have a full understanding of the principles of both UDL and differentiated instruction and how to implement these practices to realise the goal of inclusion. All learners in all school contexts can benefit from engagement and participation in

inclusive learning environments within Mathematics. There are many considerations in promoting and advancing the teaching of Mathematics for students with SEN. One of these is, an inclusive curriculum where there is a shift from content objectives to learning outcomes. Secondly, the delivery of sustained high-quality CPD and support to all teachers should be prioritised to include accommodations, UDL and differentiated instruction, ensuring that CPD targets all teachers in all contexts. The importance of teacher professional development is clear in effecting not just curriculum reform but also including all students in the mathematics classroom.

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